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**Same same but different:
Student views on the level of lecturer English and comprehensibility**

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ABSTRACT

English Medium Instruction (EMI) is a commonly accepted and adopted approach to internationalization of universities. Internationalization involves both staff and students, as they both tend to benefit from the use of English in courses. This study compares two video-recorded lectures in an engineering master's program. These lectures were transcribed and student feedback was collected on paper-based questionnaires immediately after attending the recorded lectures. Students were asked to evaluate both their own English competency (self-evaluation) and their lecturers' English competency. This paper focuses on whether 1) the lecturer's English competency key to students' comprehension and 2) there is a link between student's English competency and their comprehension of these lectures.

The results indicate that the lecturers' English competency, as evaluated by the students, for these two lectures was almost identical. Despite this, the comprehension level of these lectures was notably different. Nevertheless, students' self-evaluation of their English competency did not appear to be a distinguishing feature regarding lecture comprehension. Closer examination found more use of interactional features in the better comprehended lecture. While research is attempting to find the "good enough" level of English, the lecturers should focus on implementing enough interactional features when lecturing for better comprehension of their lectures.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Skills and Engineering Education, Curriculum Development

Keywords: English Medium Instruction, English competency, lectures

INTRODUCTION

English Medium Instruction (EMI) is a commonly accepted and adopted approach to internationalization of universities. Internationalization involves both staff and students, as they tend to benefit from the use of English in courses. These benefits may not be evident at the point when lecturers are converting and developing their courses and their materials into English and, especially at the beginning of EMI, need to use more time on course work than when doing it in their native languages. What level of English, then, is "good enough" for lecturers? Students, naturally, have to take TOEFL or other

standardized exams to show their ability to study in English before acceptance to a study program. Usually lecturers are not required to do so, especially if they already have their permanent positions and if they have established themselves as experts within their field of study.

Since acquiring knowledge on EMI in engineering education, [1] found benefits, such as more immediate and concentrated focus on the subject matter as well as concentration in general, for lecturers and students. The present study compares two video-recorded lectures in an engineering master's program. These lectures were transcribed and student feedback was collected on paper-based questionnaires immediately after attending the recorded lectures. Students were asked to evaluate both their own English competency (self-evaluation) and their lecturers' English competency. This paper focuses on whether 1) the lecturer's English competency is a key to students' comprehension and 2) there is a link between student's English competency and their comprehension of these lectures. The study attempts to see what other issues may influence the level of comprehension, although it avoids a more thorough linguistic analysis as that would be beyond the scope of this particular conference.

1 INTERNATIONALISATION, ENGLISH, AND COMPREHENSION

1.1 International universities

Currently, most European universities (of technology) have much of their courses offered in English [2]. It is one way to attract both international staff and students which is evaluated positively in the university assessment in reference to the level of internationalization of the university. When this trend was initiated at the beginning of the current millennium as part of the Bologna process¹, discussions varied from students not being able to learn through English to how they will learn both the subject matter and English simultaneously. Some student unions highly criticized the courses being offered in English only rather than in both English and in the major native language of the university in question.

Today Master's Programs in English are the norm and even some Bachelor's Programs, or at least courses, are operated in English in countries where English is not considered the native language. Despite this, many non-native English speaker lecturers still feel unsure of their language abilities and have concern whether their students understand them when they use their "broken English" in lecturing.

1.2 English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) and lecturing

Lingua francas have been used at least from 1200's when the Arab-speaking traders had to communicate with "Franks", i.e. the Europeans to conduct business. The developed "language of the Franks" (=lingua franca) enabled these business transactions to occur [3]. Since this original *lingua franca*, the term has been reserved to those native languages which are used as a vehicular language in situations where no other common language is found.

According to Seidlehofer [4], non-native speakers of English use ELF mostly with other non-native speakers of English. These non-native speakers of English have outnumbered the native speakers already for decades [5], [6] and English is the language of science, academia, business, and (popular) culture. Usually the situations in which English is used, are high-stakes situations in which participants aim at comprehensive communication regardless of the potential obstacles.

¹ See, e.g. http://www.coe.int/t/dg4/highereducation/EHEA2010/BolognaPedestrians_en.asp#P132_13851

Lecturing is a good example of a high-stakes situation and, no matter what we may think of the efficiency of lecturing as pedagogical means to learning, still a major part of instructional activities at universities [7]. With the internationalized universities, these lectures are most often held in ELF with audience whose native languages vary. In addition to the most obvious function of a lecture, relaying information, it also has other functions, such as focusing on a common goal, preparing for working life, as well as socializing students into the scientific community and even preparing them for working life [8], [9], [10].

1.3 Lecturing and Comprehension

Measuring comprehension is a difficult task. Tests, if designed properly, show what students know. The testers cannot know, however, where and how this knowledge was acquired and whether that knowledge relates to comprehension of prior lecturing. What is known, though, is that reading written text aloud is usually more difficult to comprehend than spontaneous spoken language [11]. This explains the promotion of the so-called conversational style lecturing [12] – also called fresh talk [13] and open style lecturing [14] – in order for the audience to be able to follow and comprehend the lecturing. This type of lecturing is close to spoken language rather than written text and even allows better activation of the audience, another means to aid comprehension.

According to [15], lectures in the English-speaking universities are becoming less formal and more interactive and the role of the lecturer is more of a facilitator. [16] recommend lecturers to encourage their students to be active rather than passive. These approaches, regardless of the language used in lectures, helps students to comprehend the lectures.

When lectures are in English, which is neither the lecturer's nor the student's native language, the assumption is that communication is not very fluent. Nevertheless, [17] and [18] found that ELF speakers tend to use communication strategies to explicate their message. This, in addition to other EMI features would support the learners when attending lectures conducted in English as a *lingua franca*. In other words, lecturers may subconsciously be using strategies to help their audience to comprehend their messages.

2 CASE STUDY ON LECTURES IN ELF

2.1 Background to the study

When universities modify anything, very often the first reaction of both staff and students is resistance to changes. When a Master's Program is reformed to be in English instead of the native language as it used to be, opposition is evident. Seasoned professors together with students who had been studying their Bachelor's Degree towards that particular Master's Program only to hear they will have to use English instead of their native language created a somewhat tense situation.

In order to determine students' perception of the new situation and the use of English, 22 lectures were video-recorded 2005-2006² with student feedback on paper-based questionnaires collected after each of these lectures [19]. Specific lectures were later chosen for closer scrutiny and transcribed. This paper focuses on two of the transcribed lectures and explores the feedback gathered on them.

² The material was collected over ten years ago and the situation currently may be somewhat different. Nevertheless, data itself is still useful and not outdated and, thus, provides valuable information when studied from various points of view.

Since the study is on a Master's Program in a somewhat small department, the lecture attendance was fairly low. Despite the low number of respondents, the questionnaire answers were able to shed light on the most intriguing lectures which then were studied further. The attendance influences the results of the study mainly in their generalization, but provide student point of view on the situation together with information on lecture comprehension.

2.2 Questionnaire

The entire questionnaire is available as Appendix 1. In addition to the statements regarding the respondent self-evaluated English skills and the perceived English skills of the lecturer, this paper focuses on the statements regarding comprehension listed in *Table 1* below.

Table 1. Questionnaire questions included in evaluation

		Agree	Somewhat agree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree
7.	I understood the contents of the lecture well.	1	2	3	4
8.	I did not understand the main contents of the lecture.	1	2	3	4
15.	It was easy to follow the lecture.	1	2	3	4

Although statement number 15 in *Table 1* does not specifically mention comprehension, the ease in which student follows the lecture is seen as relating to the experience of understanding. Students also had to choose what they felt was their own level of English skills as well as those of the lecturer the lecture of which they had attended immediately before filling out the questionnaire. The scale for English skills was excellent, good, fair, and poor.

This paper explores the questionnaire responses and transcriptions of two lectures that were found to be the outliers of the lectures in a larger study [19]. Based on the comprehension values and perceived English skills calculated from the questionnaire responses, lecturers in Lectures 02 and 21, discussed in this paper, had almost identical English skill levels as perceived by the respondents while the comprehension levels differed quite notably. This difference intrigued closer inspection of these particular lectures.

2.3 Results

Lecture 21 had 19 participants, one of which did not complete the questionnaire completely and had to be disregarded. Lecture 02 had 9 participants, all of whom completed the questionnaire. The numbers are used only to show trends and to provide some basic information, naturally this is not a quantitative study as the quantities are so limited. Nevertheless, numbers and their analysis shed light on how students as a group of respondents reacted to the questionnaire statements.

Table 2 below shows the respondents viewed their own English skills and their lecturers' English skills. The group of respondents is different in these two lectures, but the responses regarding English skills is quite similar.

Table 2. Perception of English skills in two lectures

Lecture 21			Lecture 02		
Responses	Student Own English skill	Lecturer English skill	Responses	Student Own English skill	Lecturer English skill
2	Excellent	Fair	1	Excellent	Good
6	Good	Good	2	Good	Good
8	Good	Fair	3	Good	Fair
1	Good	Poor	1	Good	Poor
1	Fair	Good	1	Fair	Fair
			1	Poor	Fair

Most of the students self-evaluated their own English skills as being "good" while the English skills of these two lecturers were mostly assessed as being "fair". In Lecture 02, one student perceived their own English as "poor" while perceiving the lecturer's English skills as "fair".

Lecture 22 also had one student with "fair" skills but in this lecture the lecturer's skills by this student were perceived as "good". In Lecture 02 both the participants and the lecturer's English skills were perceived slightly worse than in Lecture 22. In both lectures those students who evaluated their own English skills being lowest in the group ("fair" or "poor"), both perceived their lecturer's skills one category higher than their own. However, those students who had self-assessed their own skills as "excellent" perceived their lecturer's English skills at least one category lower than their own ("good" or "fair").

How do the English skills reflect on comprehension of these lectures? Table 3 below shows participant responses to the chosen comprehension-related statements and the findings show more differences than those regarding English skills.

Table 3. Comprehension-related responses of lectures in percentages

	Agree	Somewhat agree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree
Lecture 21				
7. I understood the contents of the lecture well.	61	39		
8. I did not understand the main contents of the lecture.			6	94
15. It was easy to follow the lecture.	44	50	6	
Lecture 02				
7. I understood the contents of the lecture well.	22	56	22	
8. I did not understand the main contents of the lecture.	11		22	67
15. It was easy to follow the lecture.	22	45	33	

The first statement, *"I understood the contents of the lecture well"* had no respondent in Lecture 21 even somewhat disagree while 22% of the respondents somewhat disagreed with that statement in Lecture 02. Furthermore, even those respondents who

were on the positive end of the scale, in Lecture 02 more "somewhat agreed" rather than agreed. This indicates the comprehension rate was notably higher in Lecture 21.

None of the respondents in Lecture 21 "agreed" or "somewhat agreed" on "*I did not understand the main contents of the lecture*" while 11% of the respondents in Lecture 02 "agreed" with that statement. In Lecture 21, 94% of the respondents disagreed with this statement and in Lecture 02 this number was 67%.

Statement "*It was easy to follow the lecture*" divided the respondents' opinions more in Lecture 02 where the responses are fairly evenly spread between "agree", "somewhat agree" and "somewhat disagree". In Lecture 22 only 6% of the respondents "somewhat disagreed" with that statement and 56% somewhat agreed.

Based on these responses, Lecture 21 can be viewed as a better comprehended lecture, although the English skills of both of the lecturers were assessed to be quite similar.

As with any study, outliers raise interest. In both explored lectures, there were those respondents who assessed their own English skills lower than those of the lecturers. When looking at their responses regarding comprehension, the responses are identical and not at the far ends of the scale. Both agreement and disagreement were "somewhat", as Table 4 indicates.

Table 4. English skills vs. comprehension

Lecture	Own English	Lecturer English	Understood well	Did not understand	Easy to follow
21	Fair	Good	2	3	2
02	Poor	Fair	2	3	2
21	Excellent	Fair	1	4	2
02	Excellent	Good	1	4	1

Scale: 1=agree, 2=somewhat agree,
3=somewhat disagree, 4=disagree

When looking at those respondents who assessed their own English skills as excellent, both felt they understood their lecturers well and disagreed with the "*did not understand*" statement. The respondent who perceived the lecturer's English skills as "Fair", found that lecture somewhat easy to follow while the respondent in the other lecture, who assessed the lecturer's English as "Good", found that lecture easy to follow.

These results indicate that the English skills of neither the lecturer nor the student. This demonstrates that comprehension at this high level of abstraction is based on many aspects of the message as well as on the participants' prior knowledge on the particular subject.

Although beyond the scope of this paper, it has to be mentioned that the transcriptions of these lectures show differences in how the subject matter was discussed in them. Lecturer in Lecture 21 was able to narrate and create a story rather than just stating facts. This lecturer also used many interactional features during lecturing to make the audience think about the subject: questions, repetition and directives³ helped in that.

³ statements such as "You have to remember!"

3 CONCLUSIONS

3.1 Research questions – answers?

As the results shown above indicate, lecture comprehension is dependent on other issues than English skills. The questions this paper set out to explore: whether 1) the lecturer's English competency is a key to students' comprehension and 2) there is a link between student's English competency and their comprehension of these lectures, thus have to be answered simply with "no" to both of them.

Nevertheless, it would be worth a further study to see what makes students evaluate their own English skills as "poor" or "fair" when they are using their English to study highly complex issues at a highly abstract level. What makes students' language identity [19] to be lower than what it actually is and is there a way to improve that self-image regarding English skills?

Another question is, whether lecturing should still be part of university studies. Similar aspects that influence lecture comprehension, however, are in effect also in any on-line materials, even when technology is called on to solve these issues.

Further studies on various aspects of comprehension and on English in Academia are needed as the way universities operate is constantly changing. Despite these changes, lectures have remained almost identical throughout decades – should they be modified somehow?

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